

The Gundegunde banana varieties of the Irob in Tigray

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TIGRAY FRUIT LANDRACES

This series of Working Papers seeks to highlight fruit landraces (native varieties) in Tigray (northern Ethiopia) in their landscape and phytogeographical context. Aside from the Gundegunde or Gunda Gundo oranges, none of these varieties has been previously examined.

The landraces include:

- Gundegunde banana varieties (*Musa* spp.)
- Tigray highland banana (*Musa acuminata* x *balbisiana*, “Bluggoe” ABB)
- Ch’elekwot and Mikael Abiy grapevines (*Vitis vinifera*)
- Michacha/Metsits bitter oranges (*Citrus aurantium*)
- Gunda Gundo oranges (*Citrus sinensis*)
- Trunghi citron (*Citrus medica*, Yemen variety)

Through field observations, brief assessments, and literature reviews we emphasize the traits of the varieties and point out hypotheses and areas needing further research. It is hoped that this will enhance future research efforts concerning these overlooked landraces.

Input by readers on this series of Working Papers is most welcome.

Fig. 1. One of the Gundegunde banana varieties, locally also called Mosohil – it was identified as *Musa*, Mutika Group (AAA). Photo Endrias Hagos.

Through history, fruit landraces in Tigray have skipped between scholarly praise and neglect. In the 16th century, Brother Rafael explicitly mentioned that oranges, grapes, citron and bananas were growing “to full perfection” in Aksum [2]. Also during the 16th and

17th century, travellers again discussed the citrus and bananas of the then Tigray Kingdom (which corresponds to the current Tigray and Eritrean highlands and their bordering escarpments) [3, 4]. Banana landrace herbarium samples were collected

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around Shire before 1850 [5, 6]; in Wag, just south of Tigray, cultivation of oranges and bananas was mentioned at the beginning of the 20th century [7].

In the early 20th century Vavilov identified Abyssinia among one of the world's crop diversity centres. He highlighted the Horn of Africa's highlands as a gene pool for barley, millet, flax, coffee, and sesame – incidentally he mentioned bananas and various citrus but did not further explore it. Despite earlier travellers' reports, Vavilov stated bluntly: "before the coming of the Europeans, Ethiopia knew nothing of fruits or vegetables" [8].

Much at the same time, Italian agronomists mentioned for Eritrea the existence of two banana landraces (Dorfu and Bizen) and two additional varieties brought in from Somalia [9, 10]. Besides an anecdotal recent mention of Bizen [11], the latter variety has been described in detail in the 1960s (Box 1), and classified as Pisang Awak ABB type by the author [1]; given the small number of fruits, we think the described Bizen variety is rather a Bluggoe type, still found in the region (Fig. 6).

In the later part of the 20th century, there are mentions of banana plants in the current Western Tigray [12], though Westphal (1975) considered bananas rare in the farming system of the central and northern Ethiopian highlands [13]. An extensive rural development study in Tigray in the early 1970s [14] mentioned the growing of banana landraces with their elevation range in an annex, and further gave little attention to it.

A literature search, using Scopus (title, abstract, key words) and Scholar Google (title) yielded only four publications about bananas in Ethiopia (one agronomic study and three

about pathogeny and pests), all related to Cavendish, the main international variety; no mention is made even of landraces. Here we address a cluster of banana landraces in Tigray, the Gundegunde bananas (Fig. 1), which grow in the valley bottoms of the Irob district and some other adjacent places.

The Irob valleys and gorges

The Irob district in the northeastern section of Tigray shares its northern border with Eritrea and its eastern border with the Afar Region [15]. The 850 km² wide district is a rugged mountainous area featuring deeply cut valleys and gorges (Fig. 2). Level lands are infrequent [16]. Situated on the eastern escarpment of the Tigrayan Plateau towards the Rift Valley (Danakil depression), the elevation ranges from 900 m a.s.l. at Gundegunde monastery to the summit of Mount Asimba at 3200 m. Most people reside in the elevation belt between 1500 and 2700 m [15]. The district sits in the rain shadow of the Highlands and, with an average annual rainfall of 400 mm, it is significantly impacted by rainfall insufficiency and unreliability [15]. The bulk of the rainfall occurs during the summer rainy season

The Mount Bizen bananas are hybrids of *M. acuminata* and *M. balbisiana* being a triploid, having the formula ABB. This has been classified by the writer, using the classification system put forward by Simmonds. The Bizen variety shows the following characteristics:

- a) The sheaths of pseudostem have very few light brown patches of different sizes;
- b) The petiolar canal is greenish with margins inclosed, not winged below, clasping pseudostem;
- c) Peduncle, glabrous, long; ovules-four irregular rows in each loculus;
- d) Bract ratio (0.35), bracts reflex and rolled back a little; bract shape broadly ovate with the apex obtuse; bract colour dark purple outside and bright crimson inside continuous to base; bract scars range from prominent to medium;
- e) The male flower shows no strong corrugations at the tip of free tepal, colour pinkish, stigma pinkish-yellow.

Other general characteristics of the plant are pseudostem growing to a height of three metres when the plant blossoms. Leaf mid-rib pale green and leaf ratio 2.1; the pistillate axis of the bunch is positively geotropic and the fruit negatively geotropic. The fruit is few in number, short and angular, with an acute tip and persistent male bracts. The above statements show that this banana belongs to the « Pisang awak » type.

Box 1. Classification of the Bizen banana landrace of Eritrea, according to Saverio [1] – the Bizen monastery is located 140 km WNW of Gundegunde as the crow flies, along the same escarpment.

(referred to as "karma" in Irob/Saho), which lasts from late June to early September [16].

The district is home to around 35,000 Irob/Saho speakers (2007 data), who possess their unique identity [17, 18]. Except for some families with a small extra income, all rural residents are farmers, primarily raising livestock [15].

The available arable land is quite restricted, with the cultivated area comprising only a small percentage of the district's overall area, partially relying on rainfall and partially utilizing terraces with spate irrigation [19]. The cultivated harvest does not meet the dietary needs of the population, and merely a limited quantity of grain can be bought with the revenue generated from livestock farming [16]. The fruits and sprouts of *Opuntia ficus-indica*, which grows either in the wild or cultivated, are crucial for the food supply of both humans and livestock. For a duration of four to six months each year, the community relies mostly on these cactus fruits [15]. Irrigated farming, particularly

orange and banana cultivation take place on alluvial deposits within the gorges [20]. For the larger part of the year, people rely on outside food assistance, remittances, and income from non-farming activities [15]. The construction of the 40-m tall Assabol dam in a gorge [15] has resulted in the mitigation of flash floods and enabled increased irrigation efforts along the ephemeral Zagarut river [21], as well as in other level areas thanks to community tankers and water conveyances, which subsequently motivated more farmers to cultivate fruits [W2, W3].

The Irob district faced significant impacts from the border war between Ethiopia and Eritrea from 1998 to 2000, as half of the district was taken over by the Eritrean army, leading to outmigration [15, 17, 18]. Again during the Tigray War (2020-2022), massacres occurred, people were displaced and imprisoned and almost half of the district remains occupied by Eritrean forces up to now (2025) [18].

Fig. 2. Overview map of the study area. Dotted lines represent valleys and gorges with strings of orange and banana orchards. Base map ©OpenStreetMap.

Table 1. Localities with evidenced occurrence of banana landraces (local names), sorted by elevation (z, in m a.s.l.)

Village	District	Lon (°E)	Lat (°N)	z	Landraces
Gundegunde	Irob	39.74339	14.37964	900	Gundegunde, Mosohil
Bizen valley	Ghinda (ER)	39.24448	15.26032	920	Bizen
Damhalle gorge	Irob	39.66529	14.49576	1260	Gundegunde, Mosohil
Dorfu	Serejaka (ER)	38.98175	15.424	1460	Dorfu
Mosohil valley	Sa'isi'e	39.64782	14.31216	1550	Mosohil
Adiha	Keyih Tekli	39.09347	13.74881	1680	Muz 'Addi
Hayeko	Dogu'a Tembien	39.21962	13.53072	1700	Muz 'Addi
Kadad-a	Irob	39.58622	14.51369	1850	Gundegunde, Mosohil
Ara'ae	Irob	39.66344	14.47518	1860	Gundegunde, Mosohil
Daya	Irob	39.5829	14.51482	1860	Gundegunde, Muz 'Addi
Gamada	Irob	39.57211	14.51279	1880	Gundegunde, Mosohil, Muz 'Addi
Alitena	Irob	39.57139	14.52203	1880	Gundegunde, Mosohil
Chikh	Tankwa Mellash	39.07755	13.55906	1900	Muz 'Addi
Dawhan	Irob	39.55501	14.51253	1900	Gundegunde, Mosohil
Shire	Tahtay Koraro	38.27397	14.10192	1920	Muz 'Addi
Rubaksa	Dogu'a Tembien	39.22704	13.59489	1920	Muz 'Addi
Beles	Tahtay Koraro	38.39515	14.07238	1950	Muz 'Addi
Ferrey	Dogu'a Tembien	39.10489	13.68019	2040	Muz 'Addi

Field investigation

In the Irob district, we conducted qualitative observations in the main Zagarut valley bottom, in a string of private irrigated fruit plantations, recording presence of banana varieties (Table 1). Interviews with key witnesses provided extra details from the owners regarding the traits of plants and their fruits. In the discussions the other Tigrayan landrace Muz 'Addi of the highlands is regularly mentioned, and our

observation locations on that variety are also included in the overview (Table 1).

We additionally inquired about how long the varieties have been grown in their village, whether they are aware of the origin of the variety, and the names of other villages where it is produced. We examined the trends of the varieties, looking at whether the population of plants in the village is rising or falling, potential causes, and the pros and cons compared to newly introduced banana varieties (Table 2).

Table 2. Key witnesses in the Irob district, interviewed over telephone; witnesses W2 and W3 were in their orchards during the interview

Witness N°	Witness profile	Interview date	Interviewer
[W1]	Senior NGO staff, Adigrat	9 December 2024	JN
[W2]	Farmer in Gamada	17 December 2024	AK
[W3]	Farmer in Daya	18 December 2024	AK
[W4]	Son of banana farmer at Gundegunde	18 January 2025	AK
[W5]	Monk at Gundegunde, fruit grower	21 January 2025	AK
[W6]	Son of farmer in Gundegunde, fruit grower	23 January 2025	AK

Fig. 3. A banana plantation on a lower terrace of the Gundegunde river. Photo Michael Gervers.

Gundegunde

In the local Saho/Irob language, *gunde* stands for untreated wooden logs. Hence, the place name Gundegunde has been interpreted as “wood collector’s place”, alluding to a larger place inside the gorge where wood that has been carried by floods from the uplands is readily deposited [20], and collected by the villagers (Fig. 9). The gorge houses the village of Gundegunde with 300 inhabitants [22], along with a monastery from the 13th to 14th century, known as Gunda Gundo in Tigrinya. Additionally, there are a dozen of inconspicuous neighboring hamlets, including Gomod, Sawne and Maruwa. On narrow river terraces within more than 1000-metres deep gorges leading from the uplands to the Danakil depression, orange and banana orchards have been established over centuries under the impulse of monks settled at the monastery [20, 23]. Following the overthrow of Emperor Haile Selassie in the 1970s, the most of the orchards were transferred to local farmers [20], and are currently under their management (Fig. 3).

Local fruit growers insist that there are two banana varieties in Gundegunde: Mosohil and Gundegunde proper [W5, W6]. Due to their height, the original Gundegunde banana plants were challenging to harvest. Only few are able to harvest the bananas, which grow at the top of the plants. To collect the bunches, the plant must be bent with a long rod. Although they have been cultivated at Gundegunde since the founding of the monastery [W5], the variety is also vulnerable to wind damage and no longer common there [W6]. The origin of the plants is unknown; however, the first monks began growing the Gundegunde banana variety [W5].

Because they are shorter, Mosohil banana trees are easier to harvest. Depending on how well the plant is cared for, a single Mosohil bunch can hold up to 300 bananas [W6]. Mosohil bananas, and some Gundegunde proper, are also found growing upstream and downstream from Gundegunde at various hamlets along the main river [W6] (Fig. 3, Fig. 9). No farmers in the gorges around Gundegunde have shifted to the newly introduced varieties [W5].

Many banana suckers have been harvested at Gundegunde, and replanted in the Zagarut valley in Irob, as well as in the area surrounding the Debre Abay monastery in NW Tigray [W5].

Gundegunde banana cultivation in Irob

In the Zagarut valley, higher up in the Irob district, there are many banana plants in irrigated lands that benefit from the Assabol reservoir [W1]. Bananas are not grown at homesteads because of lack of land and water there [W2]. Banana trees were reintroduced along the Zagarut after the Eritrea-Ethiopia war, which is after the year 2000.

The local and most common banana varieties at Zagarut are called Gundegunde; they came from the gorges around the monastery [W2]. With relatively short pseudostems, broad leaves, and tall fruits (250-300 g per banana), the plants are interchangeably called Mosohil [W1, W2, W3] (Fig. 1, Fig. 4). We notice that Zagarut banana growers' perceptions of the Gundegunde banana varieties are unclear, unlike those of the Gundegunde canyon itself.

Fig. 4. A bunch of Gundegunde bananas. The type was identified as *Musa*, Cavendish Group (AAA). Locally, it is called Mosohil. Photo Endrias Hagos.

Gundegunde or Mosohil banana harvests at Zagarut are smaller than in Gundegunde, only some 60 bananas per bunch [W2, W3], due to lesser temperature [W2]. However, in contrast to oranges, bananas are harvested throughout the year, and it is difficult to assess their annual production [W2].

In recent years, taller banana tree plants with short fruits were brought in from the Tigray highlands by the Adigrat Diocesan Development Action [W1]. Banana plants grown traditionally in the Tigray highlands are of another local variety, Muz 'Addi, which produces short and very tasty bananas, identified as “Bluggoe” (genome ABB) [24].

In the Zagarut valley of Irob, the introduced highland banana plants produce smaller fruits than the Gundegunde plants, and the trees are thin and tall, hence prone to wind damage, so people no longer prefer it [W2, W3]. Cavendish bananas were also introduced to Irob. The different introduced banana varieties have diseases, that infect the good ones—the

Gundegunde. The disease it carries does not affect the introduced bananas itself as badly, but it is very harmful to the Gundegunde [W2]. As the Gundegunde bananas are tastier compared to the highland variety, they sell better in the market. For that reason, farmers prefer to grow Gundegunde [W3]. On the markets in the highlands there is also high demand for Gundegunde bananas [25].

Fig. 5. Dwarf Cavendish (Petite Naine) type banana plant (AAA), growing near Gundegunde monastery. Photo Fissuh Hagos.

Besides Mosohil, some farmers know that other local varieties exist in these gorges around the monastery [W3]; there is a mix of Gundegunde, Mosohil and highland landraces [W4] (Fig. 5). In the Zagarut valley, the names of varieties grown in the adjacent Eritrean

valleys are not known; since 2000, the border is closed and there is no more contact [W2].

Gundegunde banana varieties

Two wild banana species native to Southeast Asia, *Musa acuminata* Colla and *M. balbisiana* Colla, are the origin of nearly all edible bananas. In literature, one might also encounter *M. paradisiaca* L. and *M. sapientum* L., which refer to familiar edible varieties that both have hybrid origins; this terminology is now considered obsolete [26].

Among the Gundegunde banana plants, we identified triploid types of ABB, AAB and AAA genomic compositions. In this classification the relative importance of *M. acuminata* and *M. balbisiana* in banana varieties is represented by the weight of the letters A and B [26].

Fig. 6. Gundegunde banana bunch and male bud, most likely Bluggoe type (ABB). Photo Endrias Hagos.

Further we found plants of an undefined Cavendish type (AAA) (Fig. 4) or a Dwarf Cavendish (Petite Naine AAA) (Fig. 5). Another plant was identified as Bluggoe (ABB) type (Fig. 6). All these plants were referred to locally as Mosohil; in addition to information passed down from the individual from whom the sucker was

taken, the lesser height of the plant and the larger size of the fruits are important characteristics utilized in the local naming.

Fig. 7. Gundegunde banana plant at Zagarut valley – identified as AAA Mutika Group (East African Highlands bananas). Photo Endrias Hagos.

Some of the Gundegunde/Mosohil bananas have been identified as *M. acuminata*, triploid (AAA), Mutika Group (Figs. 1, 7 and 8). A Group of banana varieties originates from one reproductive incident, succeeded by varying degrees of vegetative propagation over time. The greater the Group, the more probable it is for natural variations to take place, resulting in the emergence of many varieties within the Group. For bananas with an AAA genomic composition, such is for instance the case for the Mutika Group (East African Highlands bananas), which follows the Cavendish, the most significant Group [27]. Typical characteristics of the Mutika Group [26, 28] that are met by some of the Mosohil plants, apart from the classical *M. acuminata* characters, are a dark (almost black) pseudostem, dark green colour of the rather short fruits, with white pulp, shape and dull purple-brown colour of the somewhat discoloured male bud (Figs. 1 and 7).

Fig. 8. Unripe Gundegunde banana from the plant pictured in Fig. 7. Photo Endrias Hagos.

More than a hundred Mutika cultivars, categorized into five clone sets, are cultivated in the African Great Lakes region [28-31]. The significant diversity of Mutika cultivars indicates an extended duration of farmer selection [28]. How the Mosohil varieties fit among these clone sets and cultivars is yet to be investigated.

The Mutika cultivars are genetically uniform having arisen from a single clone; Austronesian-speaking navigators would have brought it to Africa early first millennium CE, traveling across the Indian Ocean to the Comoros islands and then to the East African coast [31, 32]. In this approach, some of the Gundegunde/Mosohil banana plants (Figs. 1 and 7) would be an extension of the East African Highland bananas – way north of the Arba Minch area in Ethiopia where Mutika cultivars have also been identified [31].

Possible genotypical similarity between Gundegunde banana varieties and the nearby native Bizen variety in Eritrea [1, 9, 11] needs also to be further investigated.

The Tigray banana landraces

In this study the Mosohil banana landraces were monitored in the field; it has not been formally described earlier on. The varieties were incidentally discovered while studying the more widespread Muz 'Addi landrace. Mosohil exclusively grow in valleys along the northeastern escarpment of the Tigray plateau.

The more common Muz 'Addi banana landrace that grows in the Tigray highlands has been sampled in botanical collections [5, 6], but its characteristics have never been studied. Own field observations show that in the Tigray highlands, these “Bluggoe” local bananas are grown in intervening valleys, near larger springs

that allow for irrigated gardening. As an average plateau district, in Dogu'a Tembien, in the villages of Rubaksa and Ferrey, both the local and the Cavendish banana plants would have 125-250 bananas per bunch. But the Cavendish bananas are too thin and do not fully ripen; hence farmers prefer the landrace, which is short, thick, has a good taste and is highly demanded in the market for those reasons. There are no diseases on the landrace, but Cavendish may dry off at flowering stage. Generally, farmers do not wish to switch from Muz 'Addi to Cavendish because they know very well the management system of the local varieties. Further they believe that the latter has a better taste and is more nutritious.

Strings of banana plantations to be investigated in Irob's valleys and gorges

Though Westphal mentions an optimal altitudinal range for bananas in Ethiopia between between 1500 and 1800 m [13], our witnesses mentioned that the lower elevations at Gundegunde yielded larger banana bunches. Further studies could investigate this aspect using the strings of banana plantations in Zagarut and several valleys leading to Gundegunde (Fig. 9), taking also into account banana varieties and the fertility status of the alluvium in which the banana plants grow. Such a study has been carried out in steep, deeply incised valleys in Oman [33].

This would also allow us to determine whether the Mosohil banana belongs to a particular landrace. The name refers to a geographic origin, the Mosohil river that runs in a canyon where muslim Saho speakers manage banana orchards south of Gundegunde [W4] (Fig. 2); alternatively, the name may be used interchangeably with Gundegunde for a range of banana landraces.

An additional challenge for the banana landraces here is that its temporal continuity is sometimes interrupted. With the Ethiopia-Eritrean war around 2000, the Zagarut valley was abandoned and age-old fruit plantations perished. After the local extinction, new Gundegunde and Mosohil plants were brought in from Gundegunde, as well as highland bananas and Cavendish, leading to a shrinking of the gene pool. Similar fruit plantation abandonments due to war have been described for the Tekeze valley during the Tigray war [34] and in the Inticho area around 1870 [35].

Fig. 9. The irrigated areas of Gomod, an hour upstream of Gundegunde, feature fields of bananas, sorghum, maize and orange trees. Adjacent to the farmhouse on the left, one can observe a pile of large driftwood, referred to as *gunde* in Irob/Saho, which was brought in by the rushing waters. Photo Gordon Belray.

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